

THE IMPACTS OF BAD HABITS ON THE HUMAN BODY

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Annotation: In the process of providing a comprehensive understanding of harmful habits and their effects on the human body, attention is paid to some of diseases and bad habits. The article provides information about some kind of bad habits and the influence of them to human health.

Keywords: Harmful, habits, human, health, routine, medicine, body, system, addiction.

In the modern world, the development of household appliances, computerization of production processes at various enterprises, the widespread use of public and personal transport leads to an increase in a sedentary lifestyle for most people and a decrease in physical activity. A sedentary lifestyle is a decrease in physical activity or hypokinesia. Hypokinesia in school age is associated with the child's irrational organization. Researches by scientists in many countries show that people over the age of 40 who are sedentary are twice as likely to develop hypertension and atherosclerosis. In the present world, the most effective way to combat this negative condition is to engage systematically in any type of exercise, running and walking in the fresh air, which does not require any special conditions.

Studies have shown that a person activates more than 60 muscles while walking. At the same period, regular exercise has a beneficial effect on the cardiovascular and respiratory systems, improves metabolism in the body, prevents obesity. In addition, gradually increasing the duration of walking helps to improve blood circulation in the heart. The movement of the leg during walking works like a pumping mechanism and leads to an improvement in blood circulation not only in

the leg, but in the whole body. Inadequate muscle activity due to insufficient movement during activity suddenly affects the state of the body. Because of the risk of hypokinesia and hypodynamics, patients are also not allowed to stay in bed for long periods of time. Insufficient motor activity primarily affects the compensatory ability of the cardiovascular and nervous systems. Inactivity is observed in workers who stand on their feet all day in the workplace. Working in one position all day in front of the machine ensures blood circulation in the leg, and this is done by dilating the veins and bruising under the skin. When working in a standing position on a regular basis, over time, muscle flexibility is lost and tissue mobility is reduced. Working from a standing position makes the body much easier. This increases the area of the base, does not put static load on the leg muscles, facilitates the work of the cardiovascular system. However, due to the decrease in motor activity during sitting, it also has its disadvantages due to the observation of hypokinesia and hypodynamics in the body. In medical practice, addiction to alcohol, smoking, drugs and toxic substances is a harmful habit. Putting lipstick on alcohol gradually ends with intoxication and then an alcoholic state. It is no secret that drinking and alcoholism are now common among young people (pupils, students). Therefore, combating this negative situation and preventing it has always been and will remain one of the top priorities of every state. It is very important that these measures are taken into account at the government level. Because the health of the people is based on the preservation of the health of the younger generation. Regular failure to take serious measures to combat such negative phenomena leads to the spread of drugs and toxic substances among certain segments of the population. As a result, drug use increases. Medical examinations have also shown that such harmful habits in young people can be inherited from parents to children. China's medical statistics have been in the country in recent years

- 1) serious diseases such as cardiovascular, oncological;
- 2) death;

3) shows a significant increase in injuries among citizens with harmful habits.

This results in a decrease in life expectancy (especially up to 58 years in men). These statistics confirm that 50 percent of people who die are people who have been involved in harmful habits. The impacts of alcohol on the human body have been well studied since ancient times. The famous nineteenth-century German poet Goethe wrote in one of his articles: "Wine kills people's physical health, kills their mental abilities, kills their family economically, and most horribly, kills their descendants." In the early twentieth century, the American writer D.London writes as follows. "Alcohol is the birth of arrogance, which consumes man, destroys his strength, destroys his energy, kills the brightest colour of man at birth, and has long since turned man into a living dead, a disgusting copy of him." Therefore, it is expedient to fight against this abominable evil in every educational institution, in the family, by carrying out a high level of spiritual work. Alcoholic beverages (mainly S2N5ON in ethyl alcohol) are consumed for the drug effects of ethanol. A small dose of it awakens the body by raising the mood, more weakens self-control and leads to relaxation. When a person consumes alcohol, most of it is absorbed into the bloodstream through the stomach and a small part through the red blood cell.

The rate at which an alcoholic beverage is absorbed into the bloodstream depends on the concentration of that beverage. Food slows the absorption of alcohol into the bloodstream, reducing its amount in the blood by 2 times. Severe fatigue, brain injury, mental illness, poisoning, infections reduce the body's resistance to alcohol, polluted air, high temperature and its sudden change accelerates the time of intoxication. Alcohol absorbed into the blood is mainly processed in the liver and to a lesser extent in the blood. Only 6 to 10% of alcohol is excreted unchanged through the kidneys, skin glands, and lungs. The rate of oxidation of alcohol in the body is 100 g per 1 kg body weight. At this rate, it takes about a day to process 1 bottle of alcohol consumed by the body (with enough snacks). Alcohol of any content cannot be a drug, it cannot kill bacteria and viruses. Self-medication with alcohol does not

lead to good results. Alcohol prevents the transfer of substances needed for cell renewal into the bloodstream. Doctors believe that alcohol is a poison that affects the central nervous system. As a result of this effect, the braking process in the cerebral cortex is weakened, and the control of one's character in a person is suddenly assured. It is known that people who are addicted to alcohol are 2 times more likely to suffer from cardiovascular disease, 18 times more likely to suffer from gastrointestinal disease and 4 times more likely to suffer from respiratory disease than people who do not consume it. It has been found that alcohol has a negative effect on the male genitals, even causing it to stop functioning completely. Medical statistics show that alcohol reduces the activity of the immune system of the human body, as a result of which people often become seriously ill, and many diseases become chronic.

These following bad habits are considered common habits and they can harm your health. Also they are able to be an obstacle to your future.

-Biting your nails

This can damage your teeth as well as the skin around your nail bed, which can lead to infection. You also may get more colds and other illnesses when you put your fingers, which often carry germs, into your mouth. It can help to keep your nails neatly trimmed or manicured. If stress could be the reason for your habit, you might try things like exercise to manage it. Talk to your doctor if you want help stopping.

-Cheating yourself on sleep

If you don't get enough sleep, you're not just turning yourself into a daytime zombie, you also could be more likely to have high blood pressure, heart disease, diabetes, and depression. And it might be harder for you to learn and remember things. As a result, your successful life may be late. Set a regular sleep routine and stick with it. And do your best to get 7-8 hours a night.

-Cracking Your Knuckles

It doesn't just annoy your friends and co-workers but it may not be very good for you, either. A substance called synovial fluid keeps your joints moving easily. The sound your knuckles make when they "crack" comes when you pop tiny bubbles in that fluid. If you do it all the time, you're more likely to have swollen hands and a weaker grip over time. It doesn't seem to raise your chances of arthritis, though.

-Surfing in bed before sleeping

The "blue light" given off by electronic gadgets like phones, computers, and TVs can mess up your sleep. And some studies show that too much of any kind of nighttime light might be linked to cancer (especially breast and prostate), diabetes, obesity, and heart disease. Calm yourself before bed. If you want to read something, open up a book. Keep your bedroom dark and quiet for better sleep.

-Eating Too Much

If you make a habit of it - even if it's healthy food, you are likely to gain weight. That can lead to heart disease, diabetes, and high blood pressure, and it can raise your chances of certain kinds of cancer. Check portion sizes before meals and measure out snacks you have in front of the TV, so you know exactly how much you're eating.

-Eating Too Quickly

It can leave you less satisfied, and make you more likely to overeat over the course of the day. If you slow down, you could feel fuller with less, because your body has a chance to realize you've eaten enough. It can help to focus when you eat: Take small bites, and chew them well. Even it is said that Russian people chew any meal 40 times. It means they pay attention to their health.

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